

MEASURING THE LUMINOSITY AND BLACK HOLE MASS DEPENDENCE OF QUASAR-GALAXY CLUSTERING AT $z \sim 0.8$

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ABSTRACT

We study the dependence of quasar clustering on quasar luminosity and black hole mass by measuring the cross-correlation of $z \sim 0.8$ quasars from SDSS and color-selected galaxies imaged by WISE. Because we lack spectroscopy of the WISE galaxies, we measure the projected angular cross-correlation function rather than the 3-dimensional cross-correlation function. This method allows us to achieve smaller random uncertainties than 3-dimensional measurements of the quasar autocorrelation function or the quasar-galaxy cross-correlation function. By measuring the luminosity dependence of clustering amplitude, we can probe models of quasar formation and evolution. We present a significant over-density of WISE galaxies about $z \sim 0.8$ quasars at comoving scales 0.1–6.4 h^{-1} Mpc. We find no appreciable increase in clustering amplitude with quasar luminosity, but do find a relationship between clustering amplitude and black hole mass. A power-law fit between luminosity and clustering amplitude over a decade in luminosity gives an exponent of -0.03 ± 0.07 (1 σ errorbar), while a power-law fit between black hole mass and clustering amplitude, also over a decade in black hole mass, yields an exponent of 0.19 ± 0.107 . This corresponds to a nonzero detection of black hole mass dependent clustering at the 96% level. Our measurements indicate that while black hole masses are correlated with host dark matter halo masses, a small range in host dark matter halo masses maps to a large range in quasar luminosities.

1. BACKGROUND

Although suspected for decades, it has only been recently confirmed that nearly every nearby elliptical galaxy or spiral bulge hosts a central supermassive black hole (Kormendy and Richstone 1995). SMBHs are tightly related to the macroscopic properties of the host galaxy. Black hole mass is closely tied to both the stellar velocity dispersion of the associated spheroid (e.g. spiral bulge or elliptical galaxy) (Gebhardt et al. 2000; Ferrarese and Merritt 2000), and to the mass of the spheroid (Marconi and Hunt 2003). Since the host spheroid is much larger than its SMBH, these close relationships are strong evidence that galaxy evolution is tightly entwined with black hole evolution.

Quasars are an important evolutionary stage for both black holes and galaxies. Quasar activity must be associated with massive, disruptive flows of gas into the center of the galaxy. This leads to large-scale accretion onto the black hole, a corresponding rapid growth in black hole mass, and a burst of star formation. Indeed, observations have found a correlation between quasar activity and star formation rate (Bonfield et al. 2011).

One well studied hypothesis is that quasar activity is triggered by major mergers of gas-rich galaxies. This hypothesis unifies many observations about quasars. First, the disruption of the galaxies provides enough gas inflow to trigger both quasar activity and star formation in the host galaxy. Second, quasars were much more common during the “quasar epoch” at high redshift, when major mergers were also more frequent than they are today (Schneider 2006). Third, major mergers tend to disrupt stellar orbits, transforming disk-shaped galaxies into spheroids that are the progenitors of either elliptical galaxies or spheroidal bulges in spiral galaxies (Hopkins et al. 2007a).

However, even if the major merger hypothesis is correct, the details of quasar evolution and the history of gas accretion are not fully known. Many different models have been proposed to explain observations of quasar clustering and the quasar luminosity function, ranging in sophistication from numerical simulations of quasar activity in merging galaxies to models consisting of scaling relations with no preference for the underlying physics of the gas accretion (White et al. 2012). In this paper, we consider models that address the question of whether high luminosity quasars are physically different from low luminosity quasars or are merely the same systems in different evolutionary phases. Specifically, these models study the relationship between quasar luminosity and the mass of the quasar’s host dark matter halo.

A variety of different models have been proposed to answer this question. In a highly simplified “light bulb” model, the quasar radiates at constant luminosity for a characteristic time $\sim 10^7$ yr and then shuts off (Lidz et al. 2006). In the simplest version of this model, there is no scatter in the relationship between the quasar luminosity and the host dark matter halo mass; that is, all quasars radiate at the same Eddington ratio and have the same relationship of black hole mass to dark matter halo mass. Therefore, bright quasars have a greater Eddington luminosity than faint quasars and thus have a more massive black hole and host dark matter halo.

Kauffmann and Haehnelt (2002) propose a model in which the quasar luminosity declines exponentially after a major merger:

$$L = L_{peak} \exp\left(-\frac{t}{t_q}\right) \quad (1)$$

In this model, the time spent in each log-luminosity bin

below the peak bin is constant:

$$\frac{dt}{d \log L} = t_S \left(\ln \frac{10}{l} \right) \quad (2)$$

Since the quasar luminosity function is greater at lower luminosities (Richards et al. 2006), fainter quasars will tend to have fainter peak luminosities and lower-mass black holes. As in the lightbulb model, faint quasars lie in less massive dark matter halos than bright quasars.

However, this model does not incorporate any scatter in quasars' Eddington ratios, even though it is known that not all quasars radiate at the same Eddington ratio. Conroy and White (2013) propose a "scattered lightbulb model" in which the quasar light curve is a step function and the relationship between quasar luminosity and dark matter halo mass possesses substantial scatter. As a result, in the Conroy and White (2013) model, faint quasars and bright quasars lie in similar dark matter halos, but the quasar lifetime is not luminosity dependent.

In contrast, Hopkins et al. (2005), using results from galaxy merger simulations, proposes a model in which quasars spend much more time at fainter luminosities than at brighter luminosities:

$$t_Q \propto L^\alpha \quad (3)$$

where α is a negative constant and t_Q is the quasar lifetime. In this model, the faint end of the luminosity function can be accounted for with a relatively small scatter in peak quasar luminosity: if peak luminosity varies by a large amount, the occurrence of faint quasars would be much greater than observed (Lidz et al. 2006). Therefore, in the Lidz et al. (2006) model, faint quasars and bright quasars have similar peak luminosities, and thus similar black hole masses.

Using galaxy merger simulations, Lidz et al. (2006) finds a relationship between quasars' peak luminosities and the mass of their host dark matter haloes. This relationship is physically justified in two steps. First, Wyithe and Loeb (2002) analytically relate the quasar's peak luminosity to the circular velocity of stars in the dark matter halo by defining the peak luminosity as the maximum possible luminosity that allows the galaxy's gas to remain bound:

$$L_{peak} \propto \frac{v_h^5}{G} \quad (4)$$

Second, the circular velocity is proportional to the mass of the dark matter halo raised to the one third power (Lidz et al. 2006). Therefore, $L_{peak} \propto M_h^{5/3}$. As a result, faint quasars and bright quasars lie in similarly massive dark matter halos.

Probing the luminosity dependence of the quasar-galaxy clustering amplitude can help determine which of these models is correct. Cosmological simulations have found that the amplitude of clustering about a dark matter halo is strongly related to that dark matter halo's mass (Mo and White 1996). Since quasars and galaxies reside in separate dark matter halos, we expect a strong relation between the quasar-galaxy cross-correlation amplitude and the dark matter halo mass. Measurements of the luminosity dependence of quasar clustering therefore trace the relationship between quasar luminosity and

dark matter halo mass, allowing us to differentiate between various models of quasar evolution.

Previous studies at moderate and high redshift have observed weak or no relationship between luminosity and quasar-galaxy clustering amplitude. Adelberger and Steidel (2005), measuring the cross-correlation of quasars at $2 < z < 3$ with Lyman-break galaxies, found no luminosity dependence across 4 decades in quasar luminosity, but urged caution in interpretation of their result due to large error bars. Similarly, Porciani and Norberg (2006) measured the auto-correlation of quasars from the 2dF QSO Redshift Survey and found no luminosity dependence on clustering amplitude for quasars $0.8 < z < 1.3$ and only marginal evidence at $1.3 < z < 2.1$. Again, however, the error bars were too large to rule out any particular model of quasar evolution. Other studies of the quasar-galaxy cross-correlation function at $0.6 < z < 1.4$ observed little or no luminosity dependence in clustering (Coil et al. 2007; Zhang et al. 2013). However, the luminosity dependence of clustering measurements at lower redshift is more mixed: Shen et al. (2013), using a sample of SDSS quasars and BOSS galaxies from $0.3 < z < 0.9$, found no significant trend in clustering with luminosity, while Serber et al. (2006), using SDSS DR3 quasars and galaxies at $z < 0.4$, found a significant increase in the correlation amplitude at small scales ($R < 0.25 h^{-1}$ Mpc) and for very luminous quasars ($M_B < -24$).

In this study, we measure the luminosity dependence of the quasar-galaxy cross-correlation amplitude at $0.6 < z < 1.0$, using a galaxy sample drawn from the Wide-Field Infrared Survey Explorer (Wright et al. 2010) and quasar samples from the SDSS DR7 and DR10 quasar catalogs (Shen et al. 2011; Pâris et al. 2013). Because the WISE galaxies lack spectroscopic data, we measure the angular correlation using the galaxy and quasar positions on the sky. Nearly all of the previous work on quasar-galaxy clustering has matched quasars to galaxies with known spectroscopic redshifts. Only Zhang et al. (2013) has previously attempted to infer three-dimensional clustering by measuring the two-dimensional projected angular cross-correlation function. Studies using the three-dimensional cross-correlation function have an advantage in that they only need to consider a small number of galaxies for each quasar, reducing the shot noise resulting from an uncorrelated population of background objects. However, eschewing spectroscopy allows us to select a far more numerous tracer population of galaxies, since photometry is much more extensive than spectroscopy. Furthermore, since emission from galaxies at $z \sim 0.8$ peaks in the near-infrared, we expect WISE to give a more complete galaxy sample than an optical survey such as SDSS.

In this paper I will begin by discussing the quasar and galaxy samples and their selection criteria (Section 2). Then I will present the angular clustering measurement (Section 3) and find the dependence upon luminosity and black hole mass (Section 4). Finally I will discuss the significance of these results and compare them to previous studies (Section 5). Throughout this paper, I use a Λ CDM cosmology with $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.69$ and $\Omega_m = 0.31$. All distances are measured in comoving h^{-1} Mpc.

2. QUASAR AND GALAXY SAMPLE SELECTION

We use a color-selected sample of $z \gtrsim 0.6$ galaxies from WISE and $0.6 < z < 1.0$ quasars from the SDSS DR7 and DR10 quasar catalogs. The galaxy sample was chosen to maximize purity rather than completeness, allowing us to obtain a high signal-to-noise measurement of quasar-galaxy clustering. Galaxy colors are measured by comparing SDSS and WISE imaging. In Section 2.1, I will explain our galaxy selection process in detail, highlighting the methods used to achieve purity in our galaxy sample. In Section 2.2, I will introduce the SDSS quasar catalogs and present the selection algorithm and the systematic errors.

2.1. Galaxy selection: SDSS and WISE

The Wide-Field Infrared Survey Explorer is a satellite that mapped the entire sky at 3.4, 4.6, 12 and 22 μm . We used imaging from the *W1* band at 3.4 μm , which has angular resolution of 6" (Wright et al. 2010) and is complete to ~ 17 th magnitude on average, with better coverage at higher galactic latitudes. Since we exclude all objects with $W1 > 16$, our sample is unaffected by the variation in coverage depth; the limiting magnitude is greater than 16 across the entire region of the sky considered here. WISE measures photometry by fitting a sharply-peaked Gaussian profile to each source and deblending neighboring detections. The astrometric accuracy of high signal-to-noise sources is better than 0.15".

The Sloan Digital Sky Survey imaged a unique area of 14555 deg^2 in 5 filters (*ugriz*), mostly at high galactic latitudes, using a 2.5 m telescope at Apache Point Observatory in New Mexico. SDSS achieved 50% completeness at $r = 22.5$. Photometry is calibrated to 1% accuracy (Padmanabhan 2008) with negligible global variation in seeing (Fukugita et al. 2004). All SDSS magnitudes cited in this paper are corrected for Galactic extinction using the Schlegel-Finkbeiner-Davis dust map (Schlegel et al. 1998). Astrometry is typically accurate to 0.1", although an error in astrometric calibration causes a systematic shift of up to 0.5" in some regions (Aihara et al. 2011). We use photometry from the data sweeps for the 8th data release (DR8) rather than the full DR8 photometric catalog. Many objects with $r > 22$ are excluded from the data sweeps. However, our selection process is unaffected by the data sweeps' incompleteness at $r > 22$. Since the characteristic angular size of a $z \sim 0.8$ galaxy is 1", similar to the SDSS seeing, we select point sources as well as extended sources in SDSS imaging.

Ensuring a pure galaxy sample to minimize noise is more useful than increasing the density of the tracer population. The AGN and Galaxy Evolution Survey (AGES) measured spectroscopic redshifts for 20,000 galaxies in a 7.7 deg^2 field with $z < 0.8$ (Kochanek et al. 2012). Matching these galaxies to WISE and SDSS photometry allows us to choose a color cut that minimizes the number of false positives in our sample. Color cuts based on WISE bands alone are inadequate, so instead we select all galaxies with $r - W1 > 6$. As Figure 1 shows, the vast majority of the galaxies satisfying this cut have $z > 0.6$, so it successfully eliminates many contaminating $z < 0.6$ galaxies from our sample. However, many galaxies with $z > 0.6$ have $r - W1 < 6$, particularly red galaxies with

$0.6 < z < 0.8$. In this study, we assume that the luminosity and black hole mass dependence of clustering is the same for red galaxies as for blue galaxies.

Figure 1. Redshift vs. extinction-corrected color for a sample of galaxies from the AGES survey. All points above the red line would be included by our color cut. Since most of these galaxies have $z > 0.6$, our color cut effectively removes many contaminating $z < 0.6$ galaxies. The severe deviations from the linear trend are nearly all outliers and should be ignored.

Because SDSS is complete for $r < 22$ and all detections in our sample have $W1 < 16$, any WISE detection absent from SDSS imaging must be redder than our color cut of $r - W1 > 6$. Our galaxy sample consists of both WISE-SDSS matches with $r - W1 > 6$ and WISE detections located within the SDSS imaging area that do not match an SDSS detection (“non-matches”). As a result, the incompleteness of the data sweeps at $r > 22$ is immaterial, since any galaxy with $r - W1 > 6$ and $r > 22$ will be included in our sample as a “non-match.”

We begin by choosing WISE detections with $14 < W1 < 16$ and galactic latitude $b > 25^\circ$. Since very few $z \sim 0.8$ galaxies have $W1 < 14$, detections with $W1 < 14$ are probably artifacts or misclassified stars rather than $z \gtrsim 0.6$ galaxies. We also remove potentially variable, saturated, or contaminated detections. Additionally, since the characteristic angular diameter of a galaxy at $z \sim 0.8$ is less than the WISE angular resolution of 6", we remove detections that are extended sources in WISE imaging.

We then remove all WISE detections not contained within the SDSS imaging mask of Ross et al. (2011). The Ross et al. (2011) imaging mask is more restrictive than the SDSS imaging footprint: it removes regions with poor seeing, low Galactic latitude, and nearby bright stars, all of which may contaminate clustering measurements. The final masked area is 6966 deg^2 .

We apply additional cuts to the WISE-SDSS matches to ensure that the SDSS detections are real objects rather than artifacts. For matches with $r < 22$, we remove all detections with SDSS imaging flags indicating dirty pho-

tometry (e.g. saturated detections, cosmic ray strikes, image-processing artifacts, etc.). We do not remove detections with $r > 22$ and dirty photometry because these detections are faint enough to be flagged as “dirty” even if they are real objects. We also remove all detections with estimated r -band dust extinction greater than 0.3 magnitudes.

The astrometric precision of SDSS and WISE implies that all WISE-SDSS matches should have a separation $\lesssim 1''$. A plot of match radius squared against number of matches should be flat past $1''$, with all the remaining matches coming from randomly distributed noise. However, we did not observe flattening until separations of 3–4". Visual inspections of SDSS and WISE images revealed several reasons for this discrepancy (see Figure 2 for examples):

1. The WISE detection lies between two SDSS detections, which are only a few arcseconds apart. Since WISE’s angular resolution is $6''$, it blends the two sources into a single detection.

2. The WISE detection is mismatched. In all of these cases, the WISE detection should have been matched to an SDSS detection excluded from the data sweeps. There are very few mismatches with separations $< 2.5''$, but they are the dominant source of matches with separations $> 3''$.

3. The WISE detection is located at a faint peak in the SDSS image offset from the main detection. In many cases, the faint secondary peak is included within the boundaries of the SDSS detection. In these cases, either SDSS failed to deblend the secondary peak from the main detection, or the peaks are associated with the same object and the WISE source is offset from the SDSS source.

Figure 2. Examples of cases with an unusually large separation between WISE and SDSS detections.

Left (case 1 in the text): The two SDSS detections (blue circles) are separated by $\sim 3''$, closer than the angular resolution of WISE ($6''$), so WISE blends them into a single detection (red box).

Center (case 2 in the text): The WISE detection (red box) should be matched to an $r = 22.6$ SDSS detection (light blue circle), but this detection is too faint to be included in the data sweeps. The WISE detection instead matches to an SDSS detection $\sim 2.5''$ away (blue circle).

Right (case 3 in the text): The WISE detection (red box) is $\sim 2.5''$ from the SDSS detection (blue circle), and lies on top of what may be a faint secondary peak of the SDSS detection. This faint secondary peak is included within the boundary of the SDSS detection (not shown).

Including all examples of case 1 in our sample may lead to contamination from stars and $z < 0.6$ galaxies. In case 1, if the second-closest SDSS detection is substantially brighter than the match, it is possible that a

large portion of flux from the WISE detection should have been assigned to the second-closest SDSS detection rather than to the match. As a result, neither object may truly meet our color cut.

On the other hand, neither case 2 nor case 3 are likely to be associated with contaminating stars and $z < 0.6$ galaxies. In case 2, the mistaken match is nearly always brighter than the true match, so we underestimate $r - W1$. In case 3, the secondary peak is too faint to deblend from the main peak, so if the secondary peak is a distinct object we similarly underestimate $r - W1$.

Therefore, our goal is to remove all instances of case 1 from our sample without removing instances of cases 2 or 3. We accomplish this by defining the SDSS match as the brightest SDSS detection within $3''$ of the WISE detection. This definition keeps all instances of case 3 and most instances of case 2 in the sample (since most instances of case 2 have separations $> 3''$, they are categorized as “non-matches”). However, this definition does remove instances of case 1 in which the second-closest SDSS detection is brighter than the match, leading to an overestimate of $r - W1$. By excluding such objects from our sample, we reduce contamination from stars and $z < 0.6$ galaxies.

Visual inspection of the “non-matches” reveals another possible problem. About 5–10% of these WISE detections, although not flagged as extended or otherwise problematic, are blended into neighboring detections (see Figure 3). In many of these cases, SDSS found a bright extended galaxy within $10''$ of the WISE detection. It is possible that the WISE detection should have matched to this galaxy or some nearby object associated with it, but differences in the WISE and SDSS deblending algorithms caused the WISE and SDSS centroids to be spuriously offset by more than $3''$. If these blended detections are indeed associated with $z < 0.6$ galaxies, they may contaminate our galaxy sample.

Figure 3. An example of a WISE blending problem. Circles are centered on WISE detections. It is unclear whether the red and blue detections correspond to two different objects, or are merely artifacts of the WISE deblending algorithm.

To solve this problem, we compare the $W1$ magnitude within an $8''$ aperture to the sharply peaked profile magnitude for a point source with FWHM $6''$. We expect detections with blending issues to have unusually extended flux profiles. Since the profile-fitted magnitudes weight points near the center of the detection very heavily, detections with blending issues should have much fainter profile-fitted magnitudes than $8''$ aperture magnitudes. Indeed, the distribution of aperture minus fitted mag-

nitudes ($A - F$) has an asymmetrical tail of detections with an extended flux profile (Figure 4). We expect that some of these detections are galaxies with true extended profiles. But the angular diameter of a typical galaxy at $0.6 < z < 1.0$ is small enough that only truly gigantic galaxies possess a flux profile significantly different from a point source with FWHM $6''$. Therefore, we identify this extended tail with blended detections like Figure 3, and remove detections in this tail from our sample. Since the distribution is nearly zero for $A - F > 0.5$, we impose a symmetrical cut on the opposite tail and keep only those detections with $A - F > -0.5$. Indeed, visual inspection of 50 objects with $A - F < -0.5$ shows that nearly three quarters have blending issues like Figure 3. However, blending issues are uncommon for $A - F > -0.5$.

Figure 4. Distribution of $W1$ aperture minus fitted magnitude ($A - F$) for WISE detections included in our sample. The tail on the left results from improperly deblended sources as in Figure 3, which have an extended flux profile despite being classified as point sources. Because these could be contaminating low-redshift objects, we removed all detections with $A - F < -0.5$.

Our final galaxy sample contains 855,663 objects, including 512,727 non-matches and 342,936 matches (composed of 83,237 point sources and 259,699 extended sources, according to SDSS’s automated star-galaxy separation). The cuts described above were designed to eliminate $z < 0.6$ galaxies from our sample. But we must also eliminate contamination from Galactic stars. A pure sample consisting of only extragalactic objects should display no correlation with the Galactic plane or the Galactic center. Figure 5 shows the distribution of objects in our sample on the sky, separated by category. SDSS-identified point sources are 50% more common near the Galactic plane and the Galactic center, indicating that they include a substantial fraction of very red stars within the Galaxy. However, both the SDSS-identified point sources and the non-matches display the opposite trend and are 20–40% more frequent at high Galactic latitudes. This probably results from confusion issues: at low Galactic latitudes, a galaxy is more likely to lie near a star, either masking the galaxy or creating an extended detection in WISE that we remove from our sample.

We observe a 30% gradient across the entire sample. These gradients indicate that while our sample is not entirely pure, it is mostly composed of extragalactic objects. However, the gradients are large enough that in Section 3 we estimate the density of sources separately for each healpix rather than using the average density across the entire sky.

2.2. Quasar selection

In order to obtain as large a luminosity range as possible, we measure the quasar-galaxy clustering amplitude for two quasar catalogs, the SDSS DR7 catalog with 105,783 quasars from SDSS I/II (Shen et al. 2011), and the DR10 catalog with 166,583 quasars from BOSS (Pâris et al. 2013). In DR7, about half of the quasars were selected using a uniform target algorithm based on their colors (Richards et al. 2002); the other half were targeted in other classes using a different selection algorithm and were not included in our sample. Similarly, in DR10, we only use the uniformly targeted sample selected by the CORE algorithm. As mentioned above, SDSS photometry is accurate to 1% (Padmanabhan 2008) with astrometry errors $\sim 0.1''$, and magnitudes are extinction-corrected using the Schlegel-Finkbeiner-Davis dust map (Schlegel et al. 1998).

After applying the SDSS imaging mask of Ross et al. (2011) and selecting quasars with $0.6 < z < 1.0$, our final quasar sample contained 13,044 quasars, 6,006 from DR10 and 7,038 from DR7. When comparing clustering amplitudes between the DR7 and DR10 quasars, we chose a slightly more restrictive range, $0.65 < z < 0.9$ ($N = 5,213$ for DR10 and $N = 4,234$ for DR7), because DR10 has very few quasars with $0.6 < z < 0.65$ or $0.9 < z < 1.0$.

Redshifts in both the DR7 and DR10 catalogs are accurate to $\Delta z < 0.01$ (Schneider et al. 2010; Pâris et al. 2013). In this paper, we measure luminosity using the absolute z -band magnitude K -corrected to $z = 2$ for both DR7 and DR10 (Richards et al. 2006). Note that the DR7 quasars are substantially more luminous than the DR10 quasars (Figure 6), since BOSS targets fainter, higher-redshift quasars compared to SDSS I/II.

Black hole masses are only available for DR7 quasars. We use the fiducial virial mass estimates of Shen et al. (2011), constructed from virial mass estimates based on $H\beta$ from Vestergaard and Peterson (2006) for $z > 0.7$, and virial mass estimates based on $MgII$ for $z > 0.7$. Shen et al. (2011) cautions that these calibrations are uncertain and reports an average measurement error of 0.16 decades and systematic uncertainty of 0.3–0.4 decades. Since our subsamples all contain hundreds of quasars, these errors are not large enough to pose a substantial threat to our analysis.

We observe systematic trends in projected angular clustering with redshift. At low redshifts, the clustering amplitude is low because the color cut eliminates many galaxies with $z \sim 0.6$, while at high redshifts, the clustering amplitude is also low because our sample is flux-limited. Luminosity is also related to redshift. Low luminosity quasars are only observed at low redshifts, because our sample is flux limited. High luminosity quasars are preferentially observed at high redshifts, since the quasar luminosity function evolves significantly with redshift (Richards et al. 2006). In order to disen-

Figure 5. Densities (measured in deg^{-2}) of our entire galaxy sample, all WISE galaxies lacking an SDSS match, all WISE galaxies matched to an SDSS extended source, and all WISE galaxies matched to an SDSS point source. Coordinates are Galactic, with the Galactic center at the bottom of each plot. Healpixes covered by less than 80% of the mask are not shown.

tangle the luminosity dependence of clustering from the redshift dependence of clustering, we normalize the redshift distribution of each subsample to the DR10 redshift distribution to produce a set of weights to apply to each quasar (Figure 6).

Figure 6 shows the unweighted redshift and luminosity distributions for the DR7 and DR10 quasars, and the unweighted black hole mass distributions for the DR7 quasars. To obtain a more precise measurement of the luminosity dependence of the clustering amplitude, we split the DR7 quasars into three groups by luminosity and the DR10 quasars into four groups. Similarly, we split the DR7 quasars into four groups by black hole mass. The groups were chosen to have a substantial fraction of quasars at all redshifts, minimizing the number of quasars given a very high weight in any one of the samples.

3. MEASURING THE ANGULAR OVERDENSITY

We measure angular quasar-galaxy clustering by dividing the number of galaxies found in a given area by the number of galaxies expected given the overall sky density of galaxies in our survey. Note that the resulting angular correlation function, $w(\theta)$, is not the same as the 3-dimension correlation function $\xi(r)$. To compute $\xi(r)$ from our data, we would need to compute the 3-dimensional density of galaxies in our survey using the cosmological luminosity distance, the galaxy luminosity function, and the selection function for our sample described above. We did not compute $\xi(r)$ because of the uncertainties associated with the choice of luminosity function and the difficulty of precisely computing the selection function. Furthermore, we only require a comparative measurement of clustering to determine its luminosity dependence. Comparing our measurement of the correlation amplitude to the correlation lengths predicted by particular models of quasar evolution is beyond the scope of this paper.

We define $w(\theta)$ using the number of counts N_g between θ and $\theta + d\theta$:

$$w(\theta) = \frac{N_g}{n_g A} - 1 \quad (5)$$

where n_g is the expected density of galaxies and A is the area within the imaging mask. Because the density of galaxies in our sample varies across the sky, n_g is esti-

mated by using the density of galaxies in each healpix, as in Figure 5. For healpixes with less than 80% coverage, n_g is defined as the density of galaxies in the nearest healpix with at least 80% coverage.

In principle, the area within the imaging mask can be determined by checking how many of the healpixes within a ring around the quasar lie within the imaging mask. However, this is computationally laborious. An easier solution is to place random points outside the imaging mask with a density far greater than n_g :

$$A = A_{full} - \frac{N_{mask}}{n_{mask}} \quad (6)$$

where A_{full} is the area of the ring between θ and $\theta + d\theta$, N_{mask} is the number of random points within the ring, and n_{mask} is the density of the random points, 2908.88 deg^{-2} . At this point, we transform from $w(\theta)$ to $w(r)$, where r , measured in comoving h^{-1} Mpc using the redshift of the quasar, is the distance between the quasar and the galaxy, projected onto the plane of the sky:

$$A_{full} = \pi D_A(z)^2 (r_2^2 - r_1^2) \quad (7)$$

where $r_1 = r - \Delta r$ and $r_2 = r + \Delta r$. I also substitute Δr for dr to indicate that we use bins of finite width. We then compute $w(r)$ from the weighted average of Equation 5, where the weights are calculated as described in Section 2.2.

$$w(r) = \frac{\langle N_g \rangle_w}{\left\langle n_g (\pi D_A(z)^2 (r_2^2 - r_1^2) - \frac{N_{mask}}{n_{mask}}) \right\rangle_w} - 1 \quad (8)$$

We estimate error for each $w(r)$ using the Taylor series method:

$$\sigma^2(w) = V \left(\frac{\sigma_N}{N} \right)^2 + V \left(\frac{\sigma_D}{D} \right)^2 \quad (9)$$

$$V = \frac{\sum w_i^2}{(\sum w_i)^2}$$

where N is the numerator and D the denominator from Equation 8, w_i are the weights on each quasar, and σ_N^2 is the unweighted variance about the weighted mean.

We measure $w(r)$ in the following 6 bins (in units of h^{-1} Mpc): 0.1–0.2, 0.2–0.4, 0.4–0.8, 0.8–1.6, 1.6–3.2, and

Figure 6. Left: redshift distributions for DR7 and DR10.

Center: Distributions of i -band luminosity for DR7 and DR10 (k-corrected to $z = 2$). The vertical lines divide the sample into 7 groups. The right-most cut in the DR10 distribution at $L = 10^{11.6} L_{\odot}$ minimizes the overlap between the most luminous DR10 sample and the least luminous DR10 sample.

Right: Virial black hole masses for the DR7 quasars, computed by Shen et al. (2011) from emission line strengths. Black vertical lines divide the sample into 4 groups.

3.2–6.4. The lower limit of $0.1 h^{-1}$ Mpc, corresponding to a minimum angular distance of $10''$, was set by the WISE PSF of $6''$. At smaller angular radii, galaxies may blend into a single WISE detection as in Figures 2 and 3, leading to an underestimate of the correlation function.

To find the clustering amplitude β , we fit a power law $w = \beta r^{-\gamma}$ to our measured values of $w(r)$ and minimized χ^2 . Note that because of the complications discussed above, β does not correspond to the correlation length r_0 found in previous clustering studies. β gives the angular clustering amplitude at $1 h^{-1}$ Mpc, and I will refer to it as the correlation amplitude.

Figure 7 shows the measured correlation function and a best-fit curve, using a sample of 13,044 quasars from both DR7 and DR10. A two parameter fit yields a minimum χ^2 of 5.43 with 4 degrees of freedom, $\beta = 0.114 \pm 0.065$ and $\gamma = 0.95 \pm 0.06$. Varying the minimum bin radius does not substantially affect β or γ , nor does successively removing each bin from the fit.

We check our error bars and compute the covariance matrix using bootstrap resampling. We resample by healpix rather than by quasar (for all healpixes with at least half the maximum quasar density, to avoid over-weighting healpixes with very few quasars) in case the clustering amplitude varies across the sky. Equation 10 gives the reduced covariance matrix, $R_{ij} = \frac{C_{ij}}{\sqrt{C_{ii}C_{jj}}}$, where C is the covariance matrix.

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} 1.0000 & -0.0079 & -0.0181 & -0.0132 & 0.0036 & 0.0103 \\ -0.0079 & 1.0000 & -0.0005 & 0.0068 & -0.0043 & -0.0071 \\ -0.0181 & -0.0005 & 1.0000 & -0.0036 & 0.0171 & -0.0159 \\ -0.0132 & 0.0068 & -0.0036 & 1.0000 & -0.0105 & 0.0191 \\ 0.0036 & -0.0043 & 0.0171 & -0.0105 & 1.0000 & -0.0063 \\ 0.0103 & -0.0071 & -0.0159 & 0.0191 & -0.0063 & 1.0000 \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

As Equation 10 shows, the reduced covariance matrix is nearly diagonal. Furthermore, the errors computed from bootstrapping are very similar to the errors from the Taylor series in Equation 9. As a result, we neglect all off-diagonal terms in subsequent fits and use the simpler Taylor series method to compute errorbars. For simplicity, we also fix $\gamma = 1$ in all successive curvefits, and use linear least squares to find β , its standard deviation, and χ^2 for each fit.

All three components of the sample (SDSS-identified

point sources, extended sources, and non-matches) showed substantial correlation with the DR7 and DR10 quasar catalogs (Figure 8). Although the clustering amplitudes for point sources and non-matches are significantly lower than the clustering amplitude for extended sources, all three classes of WISE objects are significantly correlated with the quasars. This indicates that while the non-matches and point sources may contain some contaminating low-redshift objects, they nevertheless contain a significant fraction of $0.6 < z < 1.0$ galaxies.

Figure 8. Correlations between the DR7 and DR10 quasars and SDSS-identified point sources, extended sources, and non-matches, using the same axis scaling as the center panel of Figure 7. The lines are fits according to $w = \beta r^{-1}$. Angular clustering amplitudes at $1 h^{-1}$ Mpc: point sources, $\beta = 0.085 \pm 0.018$; extended sources, $\beta = 0.157 \pm 0.012$; non-matches, $\beta = 0.096 \pm 0.008$.

4. DEPENDENCE OF CLUSTERING AMPLITUDE ON QUASAR PROPERTIES

As Figure 6 shows, the seven quasar groups cover a range of more than a decade in luminosity. Table 1 gives the luminosity, black hole mass, correlation amplitude and χ^2 for each of these samples, and Figure 9 plots luminosity against clustering amplitude for the seven groups. We also measure the relationship between clustering and black hole mass using four bins covering nearly a decade

Figure 7. Left: Angular over-density $w(r)$ and two-parameter curvefit $w = \beta r^{-\gamma}$ for the correlation of 855,663 WISE galaxies about 13,044 quasars from DR7 and DR10. Errorbars are 1σ , and r is measured in comoving h^{-1} Mpc. Center: Displays the same data as the left panel, but with the y -axis replaced by $r * w(r)$ to show that we measure a significant over-density of galaxies even at distances $> 1 h^{-1}$ Mpc from the quasar. The horizontal lines represent β , the angular clustering amplitude at $1 h^{-1}$ Mpc. Right: χ^2 contour for γ and β with 68%, 90%, and 99% confidence intervals. The contours are nearly circular, indicating that γ and β have little covariance.

Figure 9. Luminosity dependence of β , the clustering amplitude at $1 h^{-1}$ Mpc. Error bars are 1σ . The best-fit power law is shown in red. The 4 least luminous groups consist of quasars from DR10, while the 3 most luminous groups consist of quasars from DR7.

in black hole mass (Figure 10).

We do not observe any luminosity dependence in the quasar-galaxy clustering amplitude. We fit a power law between luminosity L and clustering amplitude β :

$$\beta = a \left(\frac{L}{10^{11.5}} \right)^p \quad (11)$$

The factor in the denominator, $10^{11.5}$, is chosen to minimize the covariance of the free parameters p and a . We find $p = -0.03 \pm 0.07$, $a = 0.119 \pm 0.008$ and $\chi^2 = 4.55$ with 6 degrees of freedom.

We observe a fairly strong relationship between black hole mass and clustering amplitude (Figure 10). We fit a power law between black hole mass M and clustering amplitude β :

$$\beta = a \left(\frac{M}{10^{8.85}} \right)^p \quad (12)$$

As before, the factor in the denominator is chosen to minimize the covariance of p and a . Minimizing χ^2 yields $p = 0.19 \pm 0.107$, $a = 0.137 \pm 0.012$ and $\chi^2 = 0.86$ with 3

Figure 10. Black hole mass dependence of β , the clustering amplitude at $1 h^{-1}$ Mpc. Error bars are 1σ . The best-fit power law is shown in red.

degrees of freedom. This result differs from an exponent of zero at the 96% level.

To verify the robustness of our results, we repeat the measurements of luminosity and black hole mass dependent clustering using different samples of quasars and galaxies. We restrict the galaxy sample first by excluding SDSS-identified point sources and then by also excluding non-matches. In both of these cases, the luminosity and black hole mass dependence of clustering is very similar to the luminosity and black hole mass dependence of clustering for the entire sample. In both of the restricted samples, we obtain a detection of black hole mass dependent clustering at better than 96% confidence. This suggests that the luminosity and black hole mass dependent clustering properties are similar for SDSS-identified point sources, extended sources, and non-matches.

Shen et al. (2011) uses a different virial mass calibration for $z < 0.7$ black holes than for $z > 0.7$ black holes. While the two virial mass indicators were chosen because they give similar results, it is nevertheless possible that a systematic difference between the two calibrations affects our measurement of black hole mass dependent clustering. We recalculated correlation amplitudes for four

Table 1

Quasar Sample	Galaxy Sample	N_{QSO}	$\log L/L_{\odot}$	$\log M_{BH}/M_{\odot}$	$\beta \pm 1\sigma$	χ^2
DR7 and DR10, $0.6 < z < 1.0$	All	13044	11.77		0.112 ± 0.007	6.02
DR7 and DR10, $0.6 < z < 1.0$	Stars	13044	11.77		0.085 ± 0.018	6.78
DR7 and DR10, $0.6 < z < 1.0$	Galaxies	13044	11.77		0.157 ± 0.012	14.25
DR7 and DR10, $0.6 < z < 1.0$	Non-matches	13044	11.77		0.096 ± 0.008	1.79
DR10, $0.65 < z < 0.9$, $\log L < 10.99 \log L_{\odot}$	All	1302	10.87		0.126 ± 0.022	4.62
DR10, $0.65 < z < 0.9$, $10.99 \log L_{\odot} < \log L < 11.16 \log L_{\odot}$	All	1303	11.08		0.120 ± 0.021	12.99
DR10, $0.65 < z < 0.9$, $11.16 \log L_{\odot} < \log L < 11.33 \log L_{\odot}$	All	1302	11.24		0.111 ± 0.021	8.34
DR10, $0.65 < z < 0.9$, $11.33 \log L_{\odot} < \log L < 11.66 \log L_{\odot}$	All	1053	11.45		0.100 ± 0.023	3.18
DR7, $0.65 < z < 0.9$, $\log L < 11.83 \log L_{\odot}$	All	2116	11.72	8.81	0.149 ± 0.019	3.04
DR7, $0.65 < z < 0.9$, $11.83 \log L_{\odot} < \log L < 12.00 \log L_{\odot}$	All	1058	11.91	8.89	0.113 ± 0.024	9.88
DR7, $0.65 < z < 0.9$, $\log L > 12.00 \log L_{\odot}$	All	1058	12.19	9.09	0.092 ± 0.025	5.51
DR7, $0.65 < z < 0.9$, $\log M_{BH} < 8.48 \log M_{\odot}$	All	1058	11.82	8.28	0.095 ± 0.024	3.16
DR7, $0.65 < z < 0.9$, $8.48 \log M_{\odot} < \log M_{BH} < 8.74 \log M_{\odot}$	All	1058	11.90	8.63	0.129 ± 0.024	5.43
DR7, $0.65 < z < 0.9$, $8.74 \log M_{\odot} < \log M_{BH} < 8.99 \log M_{\odot}$	All	1058	11.95	8.86	0.154 ± 0.024	3.07
DR7, $0.65 < z < 0.9$, $\log M_{BH} > 8.99 \log M_{\odot}$	All	1057	12.08	9.28	0.156 ± 0.026	5.55

Note. — Clustering amplitude (β), standard deviation, χ^2 , sample size, and weighted means of the luminosity and black hole mass for the quasar samples. The luminosity and black hole mass subsamples are weighted to the DR10 redshift distribution ($\bar{z} = 0.77$).

black hole mass bins using a virial mass calibration based on MgII instead of the fiducial mass estimate. We obtained very similar results for black hole mass dependent clustering using only the MgII virial mass estimates, suggesting that our measurement of black hole mass dependent clustering is not an artifact of the fiducial mass estimates.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1. Slope of the correlation function

Because the clustering amplitude β has a complicated relationship with the physical correlation length r_0 , we cannot directly compare our clustering amplitude to the results obtained in previous studies. However, we can compare the slope of our power-law fit, $\gamma = 0.95 \pm 0.06$, to other results. Coil et al. (2007) finds γ between 0.6 and 1 depending on the sample, with 1σ errorbars ~ 0.2 . Coil et al. (2007) also finds a steeper exponent for $M_B < -22$ quasars than for $M_B > -22$ quasars, and a steeper exponent for clustering at $0.1\text{--}10 h^{-1}$ Mpc than at $1\text{--}10 h^{-1}$ Mpc. Porciani and Norberg (2006) find $\gamma = 0.7^{+0.53}_{-0.67}$ for quasars and galaxies with redshift $0.8 < z < 1.06$, Shen et al. (2013) finds $\gamma = 0.69 \pm 0.07$ for redshifts $0.3 < z < 0.9$, and Zhang et al. (2013) finds $\gamma = 1.1 \pm \sim 0.2$ for redshifts $0.6 < z < 1.2$.

Our value for γ is on the high end of this range, but less than 2σ from any of the previous measurements of γ except for the Shen et al. (2013) result. A slightly steeper correlation function is to be expected for our sample: our color cut biases the galaxy sample in favor of red galaxies, which cluster more strongly than blue galaxies. According to Zehavi et al. (2011), red galaxies have $\gamma = 0.94 \pm 0.03$, whereas blue galaxies have $\gamma = 0.66 \pm 0.03$. We also measure the correlation function at slightly smaller scales than previous studies, where the exponent of the autocorrelation function is generally greater. While we measure clustering from $0.1\text{--}6.4 h^{-1}$ Mpc, Coil et al. (2007) measure clustering from $0.1\text{--}10 h^{-1}$ Mpc, Porciani and Norberg (2006) measure clustering from $3\text{--}20 h^{-1}$ Mpc, and Shen et al. (2013) measure clustering from $2\text{--}25 h^{-1}$ Mpc.

5.2. Luminosity dependent clustering

We find no dependence of clustering amplitude upon luminosity (Figure 9). Our result is more robust than previous findings at similar redshift: we measure the luminosity dependence of clustering with a larger number of luminosity bins and smaller error. We also provide a power-law fit of clustering amplitude to luminosity, quantifying our measurement of luminosity-dependent clustering. Previous studies have also failed to find evidence for luminosity-dependent clustering, but with larger error bars, over fewer bins in luminosity, or at different redshift ranges.

Adelberger and Steidel (2005) found no luminosity dependence on clustering at $z = 2$ over 4 decades in luminosity, but only used two bins in luminosity and had $\sim 50\text{--}60\%$ error bars. As a result, Adelberger and Steidel (2005) failed to rule out quasar evolution models predicting moderately strong luminosity-dependent clustering. Porciani and Norberg (2006) probed six luminosity bins over a decade in luminosity at $0.8 < z < 1.3$ and also failed to find luminosity-dependent clustering. To directly compare our results to those of Porciani and Norberg (2006), we fit a power law to their bias and luminosity data. Our data provides a much stronger constraint on luminosity dependent clustering than Porciani and Norberg (2006)'s: their data yields an exponent $p = 0.13 \pm 0.58$, while our 1σ error bar is seven times smaller.

Zhang et al. (2013), measuring the cross-correlation of galaxies and quasars at $z \sim 0.8$, found no significant differences in clustering between two bins in luminosity with $10\text{--}25\%$ error on the clustering measurements. Shen et al. (2013), measuring the cross-correlation of galaxies and quasars at $0.3 < z < 0.9$ with quasar luminosities between $10^{10.4}$ and $10^{11.2} L_{\odot}$, found no luminosity dependence over four bins by luminosity. We also fit a power law to the Shen et al. (2013) luminosity and bias data, obtaining an exponent $p = 0.06 \pm 0.10$. The 1σ error bar on our power law fit is slightly smaller than the one obtained from the Shen et al. (2013) data. Furthermore, our finding is at slightly higher redshift and luminosity than that of Shen et al. (2013). Among studies focusing on $z \sim 0.8$ galaxies, we present the strongest constraints on luminosity dependent clustering.

In Figure 11, we compare our results to theoretical predictions of luminosity-dependent clustering from four different models of quasar evolution: Shen et al. (2009), referred to as S09, Hopkins et al. (2008) (H08), Conroy and White (2013) (CW13), and a crude “lightbulb” model used by Hopkins et al. (2008) for comparisons. The S09 and H08 models assume that quasars are fueled by major mergers, while the CW13 and lightbulb models are agnostic about the quasar fueling mechanism. However, the physically motivated models S09 and H08 do not account for other mechanisms of quasar fueling that may be important at lower luminosities. Specifically, faint AGN with low-mass black holes cannot be explained by major mergers. Hopkins and Hernquist (2006) instead argue that these systems are fueled by stochastic gas accretion and may cluster very differently from high-luminosity quasars fueled by major mergers. Hopkins and Hernquist (2009) suggest there may be a sharp transition at black hole mass $1\sim 3 \times 10^7 M_\odot$ between luminous AGNs fueled by major mergers and fainter AGNs fueled by secular processes such as stochastic accretion of giant molecular clouds. This mass cutoff is equivalent to a luminosity similar to the traditional quasar-Seyfert galaxy cutoff, $M_B = -22$. The very faintest and least massive quasars in our sample have masses and luminosities characteristic of this limit, and have AGN luminosities similar to their host galaxy luminosities (Schneider et al. 2010). The quasar catalogs are constructed to minimize the number of Seyfert galaxies included. Galaxies lacking broad lines (e.g. type II Seyfert galaxies) are excluded from both DR7 and DR10 (Pâris et al. 2013; Shen et al. 2011), and the DR10 catalog only includes point sources in SDSS imaging (Ross et al. 2012), whereas Seyfert galaxies are generally extended due to the visible host galaxy. Therefore, while our quasar sample may contain some Seyfert galaxies at the lowest luminosities, it is reasonable to assume that the quasars in our sample are generally massive and luminous enough to be produced by major mergers rather than stochastic accretion. As a result, we will consider only the contributions from major mergers from the S09 and H08 models.

Each model specifies the relationship between the linear quasar bias b_Q and the quasar luminosity. In lieu of finding the exact relationship between our measurement of $w(r)$ and the true correlation function $\xi(r)$, we assume that $w(r)$ is proportional to $\xi(r)$. Since $\xi = b_Q b_G$ and b_G (the linear galaxy bias) is constant across our sample, $w(r) \propto b_Q$. We convert b_Q to $w(r)$ by forcing each model to match the median correlation amplitude β at the median luminosity of our data.

Since three of the models (S09, H08, and the “lightbulb” model) use bolometric rather than i -band luminosity, we adjust their luminosities to match the i -band luminosities measured in this study. Following the methodology of Shen et al. (2009) and Hopkins et al. (2008), we convert bolometric to B-band luminosity using the bolometric correction of Hopkins et al. (2007b). Since B-band magnitudes are very similar to g -band magnitudes, we add a color correction term equal to the mean $g - i$ for our quasar sample (0.18).

The H08 model uses the luminosity-dependent lifetimes of Lidz et al. (2006) and predicts little dependence of clustering for the luminosities considered here.

Figure 11. Measured clustering amplitudes as a function of luminosity, compared to theoretical predictions. All four theoretical models predicted quasar bias as a function of luminosity. We assumed that quasar bias is proportional to clustering amplitude and normalized the relationship to the correlation amplitude of the median luminosity bin. Luminosities are measured in the i -band.

The luminosity-dependent lifetimes of Lidz et al. (2006) predict that quasars spend much more time in low-luminosity bins than in high-luminosity bins, so a large range in instantaneous luminosity maps to a small range in peak luminosity (and thus black hole mass, halo mass, and clustering strength). The S09 model is similar to H08, differing in only two respects. First, S09 estimates the major merger rate using simulations while H08 estimates the merger rate from empirical halo distribution models. Second, H08 derive their quasar light curve from simulations of galaxy mergers, while S09 fits the light curve empirically from observations. The “lightbulb” model is the simplest of the four, as it replaces the Lidz et al. (2006) light curve with a step-function light curve that can only be either on or off at any time. Moreover, the “lightbulb” model lacks scatter in any of the steps used to relate luminosity to halo mass. Lastly, the CW13 model is a “scattered lightbulb” model in which the quasar light curve is a step function, but the relationship between halo mass and luminosity has substantial scatter. Such scatter is expected, because of the observed scatter in Eddington ratios and the expected scatter between black hole masses and halo masses, due to different modes of galaxy formation.

As Figure 11 shows, the lightbulb model produces a substantially worse fit to our data than the other three models ($\chi^2 = 25.4$). The H08 and S09 models are extremely similar ($\chi^2 = 6.42$ and $\chi^2 = 6.40$, respectively), while the CW13 model provides a slightly worse fit ($\chi^2 = 9.77$). However, none of these three models are excluded by our data. Significantly, the data cannot distinguish between the H08 and S09 models, which use luminosity-dependent quasar lifetimes, and the CW13 model, which uses a constant quasar lifetime and dilutes the luminosity dependence of clustering by introducing substantial scatter between quasar luminosity and dark matter halo mass. While the H08 and S09 models are more physically motivated than the CW13 model, this

result suggests that it is still an open question whether quasar lifetimes are luminosity dependent.

5.3. Black hole mass dependent clustering

The observed black hole mass dependence suggests that black hole mass is much more closely related to dark matter halo mass than luminosity is (Figure 10). A tight relationship between black hole mass and dark matter halo mass is predicted by both the Lidz et al. (2006) model and the Kauffmann and Haehnelt (2002) models. Furthermore, the relationship between black hole mass and halo mass is present in nearby quiescent galaxies. Black hole mass is correlated with bulge mass and bulge stellar velocity dispersion (Ferrarese and Merritt 2000; Gebhardt et al. 2000; Marconi and Hunt 2003), and red galaxies exhibit strong luminosity-dependent clustering. Assuming that galaxy luminosity is closely related to galaxy mass, this means that black hole mass is correlated with halo mass for nearby red galaxies. Evidence for this correlation for AGN at $z \sim 0.8$ is therefore unsurprising.

However, few previous studies have explored the relationship between black hole mass and quasar clustering, and none have detected black hole mass dependent clustering. Zhang et al. (2013) split their sample into a low-mass subsample and a high-mass subsample and found that the correlation length for the high-mass subsample was $\sim 1 \sigma$ greater than the correlation length for the low-mass subsample. In contrast, Shen et al. (2009) measured clustering using the autocorrelation of $\sim 30,000$ quasars from SDSS DR5 and found only a weak relationship between quasar clustering and virial black hole mass. Though Shen et al. (2009) did find that quasars with more massive black holes clustered more strongly than quasars with less massive black holes, the result was well within the margin of error. Furthermore, Shen et al. (2013) found no evidence for black hole mass dependent clustering in measurements of the quasar-galaxy cross-correlation at $0.3 < z < 0.9$. Our results provide stronger evidence for black hole mass dependent clustering than either those of Shen et al. (2009) or Zhang et al. (2013), and support a relationship between black hole mass and quasar clustering amplitude at the 99% confidence level.

Our results indicate that models in which a quasar's instantaneous luminosity is closely related to the mass of its host dark matter halo are incorrect. Our results cannot distinguish between models in which luminosity-dependent clustering is suppressed by scatter in the luminosity-halo mass relationship, and models in which the luminosity dependence is suppressed by luminosity dependent quasar lifetimes. Since it takes several steps to connect the quasar luminosity to the mass of the dark matter halo, (L_Q to M_{bh} to M_{gal} to M_h) substantial scatter in any of these relationships could lead to the lack of observed luminosity dependence. Furthermore, our detection of black hole mass dependent clustering indicates that the scatter between black hole mass and halo mass is not very large, so the dominant contribution to the scatter between quasar luminosity and dark matter halo mass comes from the variety of Eddington ratios at which quasars accrete.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The extremely high luminosity of quasars make it very difficult to observe their host galaxies and directly determine the processes leading to quasar formation and evolution. As a result, there is still substantial uncertainty regarding these processes, and many models have been proposed to explain quasars' evolution, lifetimes and light curves. Measuring the luminosity dependence of the quasar clustering amplitude provides a probe of these models by relating luminosity to the mass of the quasar's host dark matter halo. Previous measurements of the quasar autocorrelation function and the three-dimensional quasar-galaxy cross-correlation function have suffered from small sample sizes: the spatial density of quasars is low, and it is difficult to obtain a large number of spectroscopic redshifts distributed across the sky. This study alleviates these concerns by measuring the projected angular cross-correlation function between galaxies and quasars, resulting in larger sample sizes (since we only need galaxy photometry) and much higher density of the tracer population.

We find no luminosity dependence of the quasar-galaxy cross-correlation function, consistent with previous findings. A power law fit of luminosity to clustering amplitudes gives an exponent of -0.03 ± 0.07 , a much tighter constraint than those provided by previous studies at similar redshift. Furthermore, we detect a stronger relationship between black hole mass and clustering strength than found in previous studies (Shen et al. 2009; Zhang et al. 2013). A power law fit of the dependence between black hole mass and clustering amplitudes gives an exponent of 0.203 ± 0.113 , differing from a slope of zero at a 97% level. These results indicate that, within the ranges of mass and luminosity considered here, the most massive black holes reside in the most massive dark matter halos, but the most luminous quasars reside in a wide range of dark matter halos.

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